

User Satisfaction of Library Resources, Services and Infrastructure Facilities by Academic Staffs: A Study of University of Agriculture Makurdi

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*Abstract: This study assess the user satisfaction of information resources, services and facilities in agriculture university libraries by **academic staff** in University Agriculture Makurdi. The study also investigated the usage of these resources, satisfaction of the users. The main objective of the study was to explore the level of satisfaction of information resources, services and facilities by **academic staff using the library**. A quantitative method was adopted. Random sampling strategy was used; methods of data collection included questionnaire, and observation. While questionnaires were administered to users and university librarians' observation of the activities of library users were also used to collect data where questionnaire did not covered. Major findings testify that, the current agricultural information available, accessible and utilized is insufficient and agricultural information was inadequate in agriculture university library Makurdi. Current information resources particularly e-journals, e-books, databases, text books were the information needs by the academic staff in the university. The study recommended the improvement of the existing information resources, services and facilities for the user's information needs and where possible. Subscription of offline databases such as: E-Granary to access agricultural information offline.*

Keywords: Agriculture, Information resources, facilities Digital information, Knowledge and research, University library, Utilization, satisfaction, users

Introduction

It is a fact that the provision of information resources and facilities and providing the services is part and parcel of a successful and development of any Library with a view to taking an appropriate decision to improve for effectiveness and efficiency in the Library. Ranganathan's fifth law shade a light in the major justification for provision of materials as a "Library is a Growing Organism" regardless of how it is doing and terms of how is it doing what is expected to be done by provision of digital information materials and facilities. The provision of information materials, infrastructural facilities and services is the cardinal objective of any library. Therefore, the provision of Library materials and facilities in Agriculture University Library must start with definite objectives and be designed in a way to answer specific questions and gather data that will

allow improvement in the existing collections and facilities in library for better services . However, it becomes imperative to investigate the provision of information resources and facilities and services provided for optimum utilization of the resources in order to satisfy the users of the library

Literature Review

Types of Information Resources, Services and Infrastructural facilities Available and accessible in University of Agriculture Libraries

Availability of information resources plays a major role in teaching, research learning and community services, the third law of Library said that “every book its reader”. For effective teaching, research and leaning to take place information resources, services and facilities must be provided and academics staff must have access to various types of information resources and facilities in Agriculture University Libraries in their areas of specialization

Consequently, the study carried out by Vijayakumar, (2017) opine that majority of the respondents said that newspaper, project reports, subject books, CD-ROM database, reference books are available and thesis, general books, web resources are less available, his views were corroborate by Kwaghgba, Matthew, & Rhoda, (2015) Onye, (2016), Yaseen, Shiwei Wen Yu, & Hassan, (2016) Ajiji, (2017) Aladeniyi & Temitope, (2018), and Das & Parnab (2015) while Abubakar, (2017) emphasized that Databases for Research by Agricultural Scientists in Federal University Libraries in Nigeria subscribed to such as e-databases ,AGORA, AGRIS, Cab Abstract, Agricola, AFRICAL JOURNAL, AGRICOLA, CAB ABSTRACT, AGRIS, AND AGORA respectively; others are CD-ROM, MEDLINE, AGRICOLA, PubMed, Biomed Central, African Journals Online, AGORA and HINARI, CAB Abstracts, BEAST CD, VET CD, TEEAL, AGRICOLA

Utilization of Information Resources, Services and Facilities

The Library, generally referred to as the knowledge hub of higher education institutions, is saddled with the responsibility of supporting the teaching, research and community engagement Utilization of Library and information resources, services and facilities have been a concern from the time libraries changed from being cultural monuments to knowledge acquisition and information communication centers. In view of these developments librarians conceived the idea of educating

the Library user in finding, locating and utilization of the information they need on their day-today activities as Library “is a growing organism”

Similarly, Oyewumi, Gabriel, & Fehintola, (2015) conducted a study on Information Communication Technology (ICT) and its effect on Newspaper Utilization in University Libraries in Nigeria The result explicitly revealed that majority of the respondent use scholarly journals twice monthly and by monthly basis and they purposely used it for self-examination, learning more about a subject, for assignment and coursework. The study also shows that scholarly journals are readily available and accessible to the respondents. However, most of the respondents indicated that scholarly journals helps to direct and guide them on how to carryout research and do quality research. The finding agrees often by Aba, Beetseh, Ogban, & Monica (2015) Oriogu, Oluwatola, Ogbuiyi, &Ogbuiyi, (2015)

User Satisfaction of Information Resources, Services and Facilities

In the present knowledge era, the Library is considered as an important centre and is the heart of any academic environment. The libraries are acquiring different types of resources and providing services to fulfill the needs of their clients. To strengthen the collection and services of the Library the user’s feedback helps much. By considering this, the libraries user satisfaction has been the primary objective of libraries and Library professionals particularly Agriculture University Library in order to strive, survive and grow with their user’s to meet their needs with vital role by supporting teaching and learning process of the institution by continually providing relevant and useful learning resources.

However, Osazeljiekhuamhen, Blessing, &Omoskejimi, (2015) under take a study on Assess Users’ Satisfaction on Academic Library Performance. The research revealed that users are satisfied with the information resources and services provided in the Library such as infrastructure/place/space, collection /information dissemination in the Library, photocopy/scanning machine, E-books and E-journals, media services, bibliographic services, reference services, reprographic services, current awareness, internet/online services collection of newspapers etc. The findings were supported by Kwaghgba, Matthew, & Rhoda, (2015) on Assessment of Customer Satisfaction with Products and Services of Academic Libraries in Zaria Metropolis, Kumar &Ashu, (2015) on Use of Information and Resources of Central State Library,

Ambala, Haryana, Ijiekhuamhen, Aghojare, & Ferdinand,(2015) on users satisfaction with Library, sources, facilities and information services provided by an academic Library in Federal University of Petroleum Resources, (FUPRE) Library

Statement of the Problem

An appraisal provides the opportunity to Agriculture University Library to determine the level of satisfaction of the available resources and how well the Library contributes in achieving the goals of parent organization, diagnoses particular problem in the areas of provision of information resources, services and facilities, monitor progress towards specification, compare past, current and desired level of the future and identifies areas where improvement is, what the Library has or does not have yet to accomplish, what they are doing, how well they are doing it, how users are satisfy and what they need to accomplish them with evidence that the expectations of the parent body are being met. In this aspect, the only way for Agriculture University Library Makurdi in Nigeria to make their contributions worth known to the university and the clientele is by examine the level of satisfaction of information resources, services and facilities. Identify the gap on the provision of information resources and facilities. It is also critical that the information resources and facilities provided in the Agriculture University Library are well managed and utilized in the best interest of the institutions and clientele

Research Objectives

1. Find out the various types of Information Resources, Services and Facilities that are available in Agriculture University Library under Study
2. Determine the extent of accessibility of Library resources, services and facilities in Agriculture University Libraries under Study
3. Determine the extent is Library resources, services and facilities are utilize in Agriculture University Library under study
4. Determine the extent is the Library users satisfied with the information resources, services and facilities in Agriculture University Library under study

Table 1 Population of the study

Population of the study					
Universities	Academic staff	Sample	No. of quest adm	No. of ques retrieved	%
FUAM	189	26	26	17	65.38%
Total	189	26 (13.76%)	26	17	65.38%

Since the study is a mini project to understand the level of User Satisfaction of Library Resources, Services and Infrastructure Facilities by Academic Staffs: A Study of University of Agriculture Makurdi, the sample of 78 means around 13.76% is justifiable. However, at last only 17 (65.38% questionnaires were returned with complete response.

Data analysis

Table 2 library resources and facilities available

Name of the University	Information resources/furniture																							
	Print resources									E-Resources								Furniture						
Journals	Text books & Ref Books	Conf Proceedings & Technical reports	Government publications	Thesis /Dissertations /projects	Magazines	News papers	Atlas, Maps & Posters	Manuscripts	E-Databases	E-Books	E-Journals	E-Thesis/ Projects	E-Newspapers & E-Zines	CDROM	Microfilms & Microfiche	Radio	Television	Tables	Chairs	Fans	Computers	Printers	Photocopiers	
UAM	5300	43000	20000	10418	30000	2000	43200	200	3000	7	30000	23000	1200	17	8000	NIL	2	15	600	1200	130	200	10	10

Table 2 above indicate that News papers is the highest number of information resources purchase in the library (43200) dominated the available information resources in the university libraries, followed by text books and e-books with scores of (4300) and (30000) respectively. a atlas/ maps/posters and e-news papers& zines are the least information resources available in the libraries with scores of (200) and (17) respectively and the study indicated that the library has Microfilms & Microfiche. These findings aligned with that of Vijayakumar, (2017) who noted that newspapers, journals, project reports, subject books, CD-ROM databases; reference books are mainly available in Libraries. Therefore, the university library studied has all types of information resources in both print and non-print to assist their users in meeting the university Library goals and objectives to support teaching learning and research. The commonly available furniture in the libraries that are being used to ease and promote quick and timely access to and utilization of information resources are table, chairs and computers while radio and television are not available in large quantity compare to the number of users. This implies that such technologies are not fully being used or they are very few in the library. This finding of the study stresses the fact that the library in the study had computers, printers, photocopiers, and fans for easy access to the resources and conducive learning environment.

Table 3 purpose of visiting the library

Name of the University	Status of respondents	Academic																No specific reasor	%		
		To read newspapers	%	To know the current affairs	%	To gain cultural and religious knowledge	%	To gain subject knowledge	%	Assignments and other classworks	%	Research Purpose	%	Leisure and casual reading	%	To use internet for social networks chat and e-mails	%			To access online journals and databases	%
UAM	N	8	42.1	2	10.5	0	0.0	2	10.5	2	10.5	3	15.7	2	10.5	0	0.0	1	5.26	0	0.00

The respondents were asked to indicate the purpose for visiting the Agriculture university library. The respondents were allowed to select more than one answer. The study shows that majority of the respondents (42.11) visit the Library to read newspapers, (15.79) of the respondents visit the library for research purposes, while others visiting the Agriculture University library for to know the current affairs, to gain subject knowledge, assignments and other class works constitute 10.53% each; The least respondents visit the library to access online

journals and databases, to use internet for social networks, chat and e-mails and with no specific reason (5.26), (0.0%) and (0.0%) respectively

Table 4. Information Resources, Services and Facilities as per priority in Agriculture University Libraries

FUAM	Very high		High		Medium		Low		Very low	
Library resources and services	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Journals	5	23.81	1	4.76	6	28.57	6	28.57	3	14.29
Text books & Ref books	6	28.57	3	14.29	3	14.29	5	23.81	4	19.05
Conf proceedings & Technical reports	4	19.05	3	14.29	10	47.62	4	19.05	0	0.00
Government publications	5	23.81	8	38.10	7	33.33	1	4.76	0	0.00
Thesis /Dissertations/ projects	4	19.05	5	23.81	8	38.10	3	14.29	1	4.76
Magazines	5	23.81	5	23.81	8	38.10	3	14.29	0	0.00
News papers	7	33.33	8	38.10	4	19.05	1	4.76	1	4.76
Atlas, Maps& Posters	3	14.29	3	14.29	6	28.57	7	33.33	2	9.52
Manuscripts	2	9.52	3	14.29	3	14.29	8	38.10	5	23.81
E-databases	6	28.57	6	28.57	3	14.29	3	14.29	3	14.29
E-Books	5	23.81	4	19.05	4	19.05	5	23.81	3	14.29
E-Journals	5	23.81	4	19.05	5	23.81	3	14.29	4	19.05
E-thesis/projects	7	33.33	3	14.29	4	19.05	1	4.76	6	28.57
E-Newspapers& E-Zines	8	38.10	2	9.52	4	19.05	4	19.05	3	14.29

CDROM	3	14.29	3	14.29	5	23.81	4	19.05	6	28.57
Microfilms& Microfiche	4	19.05	5	23.81	6	28.57	3	14.29	3	14.29
Radio	2	9.52	10	47.62	7	33.33	2	9.52	0	0.00
Television	5	23.81	8	38.10	4	19.05	1	4.76	3	14.29

In order to ascertain the extent of utilization of Information Resources, and Facilities in Agriculture University Library studied, the respondents were provided with a list of Information Resources and Facilities to rank according to priority. Table 4. above shows the information Sources rank as per priority in Agriculture University Library studied. Majority of the respondents ranked E-Newspapers& E-Zines, E-thesis/projects; and E-databases with higher score (38.10%), (40.0%), (33.33%) and (28.57%) respectively. Government publication, Magazines and Conf proceedings & Technical reports are the type of Library information resources were ranked very low with score (0.0%)

However, on how facilities are rank in the library studied. The responses show that television with score of 23.81% and Radio facilities with score 9.52% were found to be often ranked higher in the library studied. Microfilms/Microfiche were ranked very low with the score of 14.29%. This is because; none of such facilities are available, with the availability of databases, the users might have found that they could easily print information available in the Internet, electronic books and online databases and other related articles. Another reason the researcher observed in UAM was that some of the machines to decode/access information resources such as radio and television were not functional, this made the information difficult to access and utilize in that format. So, library should ensure that these machines are working to enable the Library users utilize the resources and such information can be digitalized or stored in the Library online Database

Disappointingly, it was observed that most of the Agriculture University Library studied are not using computerized exit doors and Closed-Circuit Television (CCTV) surveillance security system to safe guard their information resources despite the security challenges in the country and users or Library staff may be caught removing information resources out of the Library

Table 5. User satisfaction of information resources

Library resources and services	FUAM		Academic		Average		Poor		Very Poor	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Adequate no of text books	4	21.05	11	57.89	0	0.00	1	5.26	0	0.00
Adequate no of reference materials	5	26.32	6	31.58	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Adequate no of journals	5	26.32	3	15.79	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Adequate no of e-books	5	26.32	6	31.58	0	0.00	1	5.26	0	0.00
Adequate no of online journals/databases	5	26.32	3	15.79	0	0.00	1	5.26	0	0.00
Circulation services	1	5.26	6	31.58	0	0.00	2	10.53	0	0.00
Inter library loan	2	10.53	4	21.05	0	0.00	3	15.79	0	0.00
Library network service/consortium	5	26.32	4	21.05	0	0.00	1	5.26	2	10.53
Current awareness services	2	10.53	8	42.11	0	0.00	0	0.00	1	5.26
Selective Dissemination of Information	4	21.05	6	31.58	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
User-Education/ orientation	6	31.58	7	36.84	0	0.00	0	0.00	1	5.26
Indexing and abstracting services	4	21.05	6	31.58	0	0.00	2	10.53	0	0.00
Printing/Binding services	3	15.79	7	36.84	0	0.00	3	15.79	0	0.00
Information Consultancy services	7	36.84	6	31.58	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Photocopying services	3	15.79	8	42.11	0	0.00	4	21.05	0	0.00
Translation services/ Language	4	21.05	3	15.79	0	0.00	2	10.53	1	5.26

It appears from Table 5 that the majority of the respondents satisfied with types of services provided with rank excellent with 36.84% on Information Consultancy services while Photocopying service and current awareness services rank Good with highest 42.11%. It is also revealed that a good number of respondents are at the rank of very poor on the level of satisfaction' with different-information services such as Library network service/ consortium (10.53%), Translation services/ Language (5.26%)

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Table 6. User satisfaction of information facilities

Library resources and services	FUAM		Academic							
	Excellent		Good		Average		Poor		Very Poor	
frequency/%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Reading tables/ Chairs	9	47.37	8	42.11	2	10.53	0	0.00	0	0.00
Adequate & dust-free space	4	21.05	7	36.84	8	42.11	0	0.00	0	0.00
Catalogues/ OPAC	4	21.05	6	31.58	7	36.84	1	5.26	1	5.26
Translators	1	5.26	3	15.79	10	52.63	3	15.79	2	10.53
Conducive space for study and research	4	21.05	7	36.84	6	31.58	2	10.53	0	0.00
Circulation services	4	21.05	1	5.26	10	52.63	1	5.26	3	15.79
Internet facility	0	0.00	6	31.58	5	26.32	4	21.05	4	21.05
Drinking water	0	0.00	4	21.05	8	42.11	2	10.53	4	21.05
Rest Room / Toilet facilities	3	15.79	5	26.32	8	42.11	1	5.26	1	5.26
Adequate Lightening/ventilation	4	21.05	0	0.00	9	47.37	3	15.79	3	15.79
Parking facilities	3	15.79	5	26.32	4	21.05	4	21.05	1	5.26
Uninterrupted power supply	4	21.05	2	10.53	9	47.37	2	10.53	1	5.26

Table 6 above reveals that most of the Library users are very satisfied with facilities in the libraries studied with a higher score of 52.63% Average from circulation services, followed by Adequate Lightening/ventilation,

Uninterrupted power supply and Reading tables/ Chairs with 47.37%, Adequate & dust-free space and Rest Room / Toilet facilities with 42.11% each rank as Average. The respondents were also satisfied with the Catalogues/ OPAC and Conducive space for study and research with 36.84% rank as Good

Recommendations for provisions of information resources and facilities

1. Provision of Facilities which are in high demand amongst the users, based on the needs of the different types of users, textbooks, journals, offline databases, e.g., E-Granary and other resources are to be procured by the Library. The responses to the questionnaire suggest that the users, especially academic staff, prefer to have many copies of prescribed journals and textbooks in the Library. The Post-graduates and academic staff suggested that apart from textbooks, reference books and periodicals should also be added to the existing collection.

2. With the advent of networking, internet and the information explosion the contemporary academic and students have these newfangled technologies, chances are more for most of them to access the information resources in the Library online rather than physically visiting the Library. If provisions are made in the Library to capture the information resource usage of these users, who access the Library through computer networks greater insights about the level of utilization could be gained. Library staff also requires in house training programmes on how to use these new technologies and information retrieval techniques so that they can give valuable inputs to the Library users. Findings reveal that the users hardly approach the Library staff for any assistance but not as to the reasons for such a scenario. It could either be because that (a) the Library staff are not well trained to assist the users, or (b) the staff are not fully cognizant of all the resources available in the Library, or (c) the staff are not skilled enough to guide in use of various information resources, especially e-resources, or (d) lack the communication skills to share their knowledge with the users. Whatever reason, the ultimate losers are both the information providers and users of the Library resources and facilities. The Library staff would be upset or the security of at risk if maximum utilization of the existing information resources and facilities are not happening and the users would regret that they could not get on time information needed for their teaching, learning and research.

3. It is essential to train the Library staff on all these aspects and improve their relationships and skills. Efforts could also be made to create a comprehensive Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs) module about the availability, location and ways and means of using these facilities which would prove very useful for the end user.

4. Subscription to different digital information resources and e-databases is warranted so that the users will have access to different types of information resources necessary for their academic pursuit and research work. With the advent of internet and information explosion, it has become almost impossible to physically acquire the different resources you're required in the Library and if the Library could subscribe to different online and offline databases the user could access any information they need in the library.

Conclusion

This study has explored the degree to which specific information resources and services are provided to Agriculture University Libraries in Nigeria. The study also found that both print and electronic information resources played an essential role in the academic pursuits of the academic staff Agriculture University Libraries under study

The researcher has attempted to know the existing information resources and facilities in the respective university libraries and also to carry their assessment by the respondents so as to know their information requirements. The study has analyzed various issues related to the utilization of the existing Library resources, facilities available provided to the users in the Agriculture University Libraries in country.

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